

Comparison of Fast Frequency Response Methods in the Low-Inertia Grid of Cyprus

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Introduction

Proposed solution

Test System and Experimental Results

Conclusion and Future Work

Introduction

Nowadays Power system face frequency stability problems because:

- Traditionally synchronous generators were the only entity in the system which are responsible to stabilize the system with their inertia.
- Renewable Energy Sources which dramatically increased over the last years can not provide frequency regulation.
- In low inertia systems even a small case event can jeopardize the stability.

RES (%)	Max RoCoF (Hz/s)	Nadir (Hz)	Time to Nadir (s)	UFLS	Post-fault Frequency Steady State (Hz)
0	0.40	48.99	4.6	1 st (4%)	49.58
5	0.42	48.87	3.3	2 nd (8%)	49.70
15	0.48	48.79	3.5	3 rd (11%)	49.74
30	0.62	48.67	2.8	4 th (19%)	49.97
50	0.90	48.44	2.1	6 th (27%)	50.04
70	Blackout				

Challenges

- Loss of traditional "dispatchable" generation and control → new and faster dynamics, changing fault characteristics, new control requirements
- Distributed intermittent generation, new consumption profiles and patterns, unknown consumer response → increased uncertainty and congestion problems
- Power systems are pushed to operate closer to their limits → increased stability and security problems

Our Approach

- Design Battery Energy Storage System with frequency congestion control
- Implement five different types of controllers.
- Each controllers have different responses and parameters.
- Evaluation of their response using the Cyprus Power System by running realistic scenarios with and without the BESS connected.

- Implement frequency regulation controllers most suitable for BESS to contribute during disturbance.
- Increase the reliability of the system and minimize the chance of Under Frequency Load Shedding (UFLS) activation.
- Promote environmental sustainability with the reduction of carbon emissions and the increased share of RES.

- Five controllers for the frequency regulation by GFL inverters were designed using the software DigSilent PowerFactory®.
- All five controllers were implemented in a small Testing grid to evaluate their individual performance but also in the Cyprus Power system.
- All five controllers were tested to determine the most suitable battery size based on their energy consumption and frequency nadir during the fault.
- A comparative study was conducted to analyze the advantages and disadvantages of each controller for the Cyprus Power System.

Controllers Design

- Step response based on Frequency
- Proportional based on Frequency
- Step response based on RoCoF
- Proportional based on RoCoF
- Proportional based on Frequency/RoCoF

Cyprus Power System

The system includes :

- 26 generators, which include steam, gas and diesel power plants.
 - 155 MW of wind farms
 - 656 MW of photovoltaic capacity
- Distributed photovoltaic generation is connected in the distribution network with consumers, split into 14 groups.
- Each group is a different stage of UFLS activation protection.

Scenarios

- We can see the details of each scenario and also the charging levels for RES and Load.
- We will analyze the 9th scenario which is considered as the most significant disturbance scenario.
- Without BESS there was a loss of consumption of 43MW (4% of the total load).

No. of Scenario	Load (MW)	RES (MW)	Disturbance (MW)	FCR (MW/0.5Hz)	Inertia (MWs)	Nadir (Hz)	RoCoF (Hz/s)
1	Low	Low	80	87	4164	48.97	0.38
2		Moderate		77	3709	48.89	0.43
3		High		77	3034	48.87	0.53
4	Moderate	Low	95	100	6754	49.01	0.28
5		Moderate		100	6602	48.99	0.32
6		High		95	5481	48.96	0.38
7	High	Low	110	118	9410	49.1	0.25
8		Moderate		118	8846	49.01	0.27
9		High		118	7273	48.98	0.31

Charging Levels	Power (MW)		
	Low	Moderate	High
RES	50	150	350
Load	575	825	1075

Frequency Response of all five controllers

Results with Variable Capacity

- The goal was to observe the amount of power each controller needs for every scenario while reaching the same frequency nadir 49.0 Hz.
- Only RoCoF proportional controller needs a substantially higher power input to maintain a frequency above 49 Hz compared to the other controllers.

No. of Scenario	Nominal Power (MW)	Energy Consumption (MWh)	Nadir (Hz)
1	8.5/8/11/8/7.5	0.07/0.1/0.02/0.1/0.09	49
2	16/15.5/30/15.5/14.5	0.16/0.18/0.07/0.18/0.19	
3	17.5/17.5/30/17/16	0.16/0.2/0.07/0.2/0.21	
4	-	-	49.01
5	3.5/3.5/6/3.5/3.5	0.03/0.04/0.01/0.04/0.05	49
6	12/11/17/11/10.5	0.11/0.13/0.03/0.13/0.14	
7	-	-	49.1
8	-	-	49.01
9	9/8/15/8/8	0.09/0.1/0.03/0.09/0.11	49

The values of each controller is presented with A/B/C/D/E, where A refer to controller 1 (frequency Proportional), B (frequency Step), C (RoCoF Proportional) , D (RoCoF Step), E (Frequency/RoCoF proportional).

Results with fixed capacity of 20MW

- This table give as all the details we need to evaluate our controllers.
- We can clearly observe the different Nadir frequencies for the same event and understand the significance of a proper controller.

No. of Scenario	Energy (MWh) A/B/C/D/E	Nadir (Hz)
1	0.13/0.24/0.03/0.23/0.22	49.31/49.36/49.20/49.38/49.41
2	0.18/0.24/0.04/0.23/0.25	49.13/49.19/48.99/49.21/49.25
3	0.18/0.24/0.04/0.23/0.25	49.11/49.12/48.99/49.13/49.19
4	0.13/0.24/0.03/0.00/0.22	49.36/49.42/49.30/49.01/49.45
5	0.14/0.24/0.03/0.23/0.23	49.33/49.38/49.24/49.39/49.42
6	0.15/0.24/0.04/0.23/0.24	49.23/49.26/49.08/49.27/49.30
7	0.13/0.24/0.03/0.00/0.23	49.36/49.42/49.32/49.10/49.44
8	0.14/0.24/0.03/0.00/0.23	49.33/49.38/49.28/49.01/49.41
9	0.17/0.24/0.04/0.23/0.24	49.24/49.27/49.09/49.28/49.30

The values of each controller is presented with A/B/C/D/E, where A refer to controller 1 (frequency Proportional), B (frequency Step), C (RoCof Proportional) , D (RoCoF Step), E (Frequency/RoCoF proportional).

Perspectives of each controller

Control Mode	Frequency Proportional (P-f)	Frequency Step	RoCoF Proportional (P-df/dt)	RoCoF Step	Frequency/RoCoF Proportional (P-f,df/dt)
Improved Nadir	✓✓	✓✓✓	✓	✓✓✓	✓✓✓
Improved Initial RoCoF	Low	Low	Low	Low	Low
Improved Steady State	✓✓	✗	✗	✗	✓✓
Adaptive Response	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓
Energy Consumption	Moderate	High	Low	High	High
Symmetric Operation	✓	✗	✓	✗	✓

- Summarizing from the results of all experiments, each controller type has different perspectives.
- With this view we can say that the best selection would be the Frequency/RoCoF proportional controller.

Conclusion

- This paper provides insights on different controller types and proves their necessity for a proper sizing of the BESS.
- We can safely increase the penetration of RES into the system.
- This kind of frequency regulation of BESS will increase the reliability of the transmission system by preventing UFLS.
- All our objectives can be achieved with the use of each and every one of this controllers.

Future Work

- An economic overview on the cost of the BESS taking into consideration the safe decommission of conventional plants the reduction of green fines and the higher share of RES in the grid.
- Last but not least an AI algorithm can be developed and trained to pick the most suitable controller after an event with the lower consumption possible that can maintain the frequency to our desired levels.

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